
D-2.3 Development of a tool for systematic risk-assessment

Workpackage 2

Task 2.2

Responsible Partner: APHA

Contributing partners: All partners

GENERAL INFORMATION

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D-2.3 DEVELOPMENT OF TOOL FOR SYSTEMATIC RISK-ASSESSMENT

Development of a decision support application to aid risk assessors, and other stakeholders, to select the most appropriate risk assessment methodology.

With the diversity of Risk Assessment approaches publicly available, it can be challenging for risk assessors to decide on a risk assessment method suitable to their circumstances. It is the aim of this tool to aid in this process; to evaluate the constraints and needs of the risk assessment and output the most useful method of achieving those needs. The methods displayed in this tool may be risk ranking tools such as the MINTRISK tool from the Netherlands, rapid characterisation tools, such as the SPARE tool from DEFRA, or qualitative and quantitative risk assessment frameworks, such as the HAIRS framework. The approaches were categorised by how quickly they could generate outputs, their level of specificity, the risk criteria they consider, and the amount of data available to their users.

An early prototype decision tree has been developed in HTML, using a limited number of publicly available quantitative risk assessment tools and disease prioritization tools. A webinar was held on 6th September to introduce the tool to partners in COHESIVE. At the annual meeting a session was held to refine the questions developed for the decision tree within the tool. The participants were mainly focused on the priority of requirements for risk analysis techniques. Refining the questions ensures the tool weighs the features of different risk assessment techniques in line with the priorities of the user. Current work is focused on further improvements to the usability and additional content of the tool. The prototype tool was also demonstrated at the annual meeting and is now available online for the partners to access and trial.

The tool can be accessed from <https://rawcdn.githack.com/RDewar/Decision-support-tool-EJP/11dc62078461ce5f1508cbcd8f1e7c427fa22186/Workingtool1.html>

An offline bundle is available on request if there are access issues email: Rob.Dewar@apha.gov.uk

1. Development of methodology

The aim is to develop a semi-automated tool to help decide which method/model (or multiple methods/models) is most appropriate to use for a risk assessment in a specific situation. Although the one-health risk assessment is the focus of the project, the methods and models included in the tool are also applicable to sector specific risk assessment selection. Building on D-2.1 Inventory of tools for risk assessment, the methodology used was a nested decision tree. The user is guided through a series of questions that are presented in a specific order. The answer to each question defines the next question presented eventually outputting the most appropriate risk assessment method/tool for the user.

The questions and answers are written in a JSON data structure, meaning that they can be easily adapted without changing the code itself. Each node has an 'answer', 'question' and 'response' attribute which is read by the Javascript and converted in to buttons and text. By keeping the information technology development simple and generic the framework of the tool can be easily reused by other sectors that are implementing a decision tree approach. Through the use of common IT languages the application is portable across systems and sectors, there is a compatibility issue with some web browsers (such as Internet Explorer), however the application is compatible with freely available browsers (such as Google Chrome).

The resulting interface to the application is also deliberately simplistic, meaning that the framework may be applied to many decision-making applications. When an outcome is reached, there is a link to the method/model and some information about it.

The application aids users in selecting one or more of the included risk assessment methods/models, however it does not make an assessment on the validity of the models/methods themselves. The assessment of risk assessment methods is the subject of other European projects, such as [G-RAID](#).

2. Development of content

Please see deliverable D-2.1 for the list of risk assessment and prioritization tools that were included in the prototype decision support tool.

Sustainability and maintainability are core requirements of the the application, the structure itself allows for easily updating the content as new methods and models are identified through on-going literature review in the area of risk assessment.

Where the application has been presented at meetings and conferences feedback on the content has been sought. Maintaining professional networks of risk assessors will aid in the ongoing development of content for the application.

3. Further refinements

During the COHESIVE working group meetings and annual meetings feedback on all aspects of the application was sought. One of the main dependencies for the application methodology is the order of presentation of questions. Risk assessment professionals from the COHESIVE project were used to ensure that the questions included in the applications harmonized with the priorities of risk assessors undertaking completion of risk assessments. Although their priorities for risk assessment differed slightly between countries there was good general agreement on the presentation of questions and there are no plans to make changes currently.

One major activity identified at the annual meeting was a possible link to the outputs of workpackage 4. An interaction with the platform being developed here would allow sampling numbers and metadata availability to be taken into account when selecting a method/model. This possibility will be further explored in the final year of the project.

Further smaller improvements identified were to introduce an audit trail output to ensure that selection of methods/models is documented and can be easily included in reports. The text that is included in the model will also be refined to highlight the potential issues in using the application, e.g. that assessment of the methods is not included. These points will be addressed in year 3 of the project.

4. Dissemination activities

Presentations:

COHESIVE Annual Meeting 2th – 29th November 2019, Rome, Italy

APHA Science Seminars 12th November 2019, Weybridge, UK

Webinar Task 2.2 Application presentation, 4th September 2019, COHESIVE partners

Posters:

Deciding on a method: A decision support tool for One Health risk assessment. Dewar R, et al.
Poster, One Health In Action – HAIRS, 7th November 2019, Birmingham, UK

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Deciding on a Method: A Decision Support Tool for OneHealth Risk Assessment

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Introduction

With the diversity of Risk Assessment approaches publicly available, it can be challenging for risk assessors to decide on a risk assessment method suitable to their circumstances. It is the aim of this tool to aid in this process; to evaluate the constraints and needs of the risk assessment and output the most useful method of achieving those needs. The methods displayed in this tool may be risk ranking tools such as the MINTRISK tool from the Netherlands, rapid characterisation tools, such as the SPARE tool from DEFRA, or qualitative and quantitative risk assessment frameworks, such as the HAIRS framework. The approaches were categorised by how quickly they could generate outputs, their level of specificity, the risk criteria they consider, and the amount of data available to their users.

The Approaches Considered

These approaches were compiled from the publicly available tools and frameworks published by Competent Authorities and Research Institutes worldwide. This list is not exhaustive and is likely to expand further as the decision support tool develops.

Risk Assessment Approach	Description
Belgian Multidisciplinary evidence based prioritisation tool	Built in collaboration between the CDC and the University of Liege, it consider public health impacts of a range of diseases in Europe.
HAIRS RA Framework	The Human Animal Infections and Risk Surveillance (HAIRS) framework is designed to consider all emerging OneHealth to the UK, summarising them in to a concise, rapid and in depth report.
MINTRISK	'Method for Integrated RISK assessment', specialising in vector borne animal diseases. The risk estimation is optimised for disease incursion in to and transfer between European countries, ranking the parameterised diseases in terms of risk severity.
SPARE	A generic tool for disease risk estimation, built in a web-based app. This tool will be able to rank diseases based on a range of criteria. The 'weight' that you attribute to criteria, depending on their perceived importance, will affect the ranking of the diseases.
Multicriteria based food borne parasitising system	The criteria in this tool were defined by expert opinion, ranking parasitic diseases in global terms. Their distribution, morbidity, and social, trade and economic impacts on host countries were assessed in tandem, weighted with an 85% bias towards public health.
D2R2	This tool ranks the risk to economic, social, veterinary and public health factors of different diseases in to the UK based on triaged data that is kept up to date.
Prioritisation of companion animal diseases tool	This is the only known risk assessment tool working with companion animals. It is hence a good starting point for anyone looking to create risk tool involving companion animals
ECCDC tool for the prioritisation of infectious diseases	This tool is useful when information is limited but you still need a rapid output. It calculates the risk or impact of user-defined criteria and disease, ranking them in terms of severity. It is recommended to use this to supplement a full qualitative risk assessment.
Simplified generic prioritisation tool (France)	The tool is written by ANSES in French. It is a good way to estimate a large number of risks and impacts. This will provide a numeric risk and uncertainty estimate.
Emerging Threat Highlight Report	This tool was designed to identify, assess and report on the threats and vulnerabilities entering the UK. It encompasses actual impact, potential impact, and public perception. Crucially ETHIR is not limited to disease threats; threats such as the Icelandic dust cloud are known to have been assessed using this tool.
Monte Carlo Simulation	This form of simulation relies on random sampling from a distribution of epidemiological data to work out basic probabilities and risks of an event occurring. These may then aggregate prevalence and probability in to a cumulative risk.
OIE quantitative risk assessment guidance	This will provide the very basics of quantitative risk assessment. Applications such as Matlab, @Risk, R and Python are widely used in these risk assessments and building such risk assessments are good ways of attributing numerical risk to a range of criteria and to specific situations.
OIE qualitative risk assessment framework	This framework is applicable to most if not all health-related risk assessments, and divides the process in to clearly defined segments. Most other qualitative frameworks are based in some way on this guidance document.
IDM Risk of incursion tool	This tool continues to be used to inform policy in the UK. This multi-criteria decision analysis tool is effective at aggregating data from a wide range of sources, and converting this in to a risk.

Tool Details

Users	Stakeholders	Contributors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk Assessors Risk Managers Policy Advisers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not necessarily users Have an interest in the coverage of the tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk Assessors Researchers Developers

Structure

The tool behaves like a decision tree:

- The tool poses a question and displays a list of answers
- Each answer will reveal a the next question
- Questions differ depending on the answers to previous questions
- They narrow down the topic to that of particular tools

The questions and answers are written in a JSON data structure, meaning that they can be easily adapted without changing the code itself. Each node has an 'answer', 'question' and 'response' attribute which is read by the Javascript and converted in to buttons and text.

EJP decision making tool

To use you require a rapid output to your risk assessment?

Which of the following best describes your requirements with regards to a risk assessment method?

A rapid risk assessment tool with simple numerical output or complex probabilities?

Rapid qualitative risk assessment method, including a report on disease burden distribution?

Risk assessment specifically for emerging threats?

HAIRS RA Framework

The Human Animal Infections and Risk Surveillance (HAIRS) group operates across all sectors of OneHealth in the UK to detect emerging zoonotic and zoonotic threats. HAIRS Commissioned threat to a zoonotic risk assessment tool to help us better understand zoonotic risks and to assess the impact of zoonotic threats on human health.

The resulting interface is also deliberately simplistic, meaning that the framework may be applied to many decision making applications. When an outcome is reached, there is a link to that tool and some information about it.

Categorisation of the risk assessment approaches

By passing through the tool, the following factors are considered, and the user is directed towards one of three risk assessment approaches.

Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)

Avis de l'Anses relatif à une méthode de hiérarchisation des maladies animales exotiques et présentes en France.

ANSES

FIG 1: Flow chart showing the considerations in decision

Qualitative Risk Assessment Frameworks

Public Health England

Handbook on Import Risk Analysis for Animals and Animal Products

Volume 1

2nd Edition, 2010

Introduction and qualitative risk analysis

Human Animal Infections and Risk Surveillance (HAIRS) group

Processes of risk assessment

Date: 19 November 2010

Quantitative Risk Assessment Frameworks

Handbook on Import Risk Analysis for Animals and Animal Products

Volume 2

1st Edition, 2004

Quantitative risk assessment

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Murray, N. Handbook on import risk analysis for animals and animal products: quantitative risk assessment. Vol. 2. 2004. Office international des épiphytotes.

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